

Constraints and Challenges in Implementing Text-Based Teaching in Particular Contexts

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on exploring the constraints and challenges faced by teachers and students when implementing text-based teaching in specific contexts. Text-based teaching has been proven to have a significant impact on the principles of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching and learning, improving students' ability to understand the meaning and fostering communication competence in authentic environments. However, despite its benefits, various obstacles and challenges hinder the successful implementation of this approach. These constraints include a lack of vocabulary and grammar acquisition, inadequate English language skills in context, low motivation, limited learning autonomy, and lack of cooperation among students. In addition, teachers also face challenges such as selecting appropriate authentic texts, modifying and adapting them to meet instructional objectives, designing appropriate tasks, and overcoming potential student boredom with routine activities. To overcome these barriers, teachers need to engage in comprehensive professional development to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for effective implementation of text-based teaching. In addition, policymakers are encouraged to provide advanced training opportunities in this area, allowing teachers to improve their teaching practices.

INTRODUCTION

We live in a textual world, surrounded by texts everywhere, spoken, written, offline, and online. We live with the language in the form of texts, not lists of vocabulary words or grammar rules (Mickan, 2011). People create the language in texts for real-world communication, not just as isolated sentences (Thornbury, 2005). Communicators exchange meaning when they communicate. When people communicate meaningfully with one another, they create a text together. When people write for others, they are also creating texts (Agustien, 2020).

Language teachers have a long tradition of separating vocabulary and grammar from texts. Language is viewed as a collection of components that can be assembled to create a message, much like a large collection of Lego bricks (Mickan, 2011). Grammatical objects are first introduced during instruction so that students can recognize them as pieces that need to be put together to form pre-planned sentence patterns (Mickan, 2011). It is necessary to learn the rules for assembling parts into patterns. The sequencing of grammatical items and word lists is unrelated to the texts that students may need for communication. Grammatical rules and forms are illustrated in sentences or dialogues that have been decontextualized (Mickan, 2011). In meaningless exercises, grammar is repeatedly used. Vocabulary words are memorized as lists and tested in ineffective gap-filling exercises (Mickan, 2011).

The preceding statements imply that we should expose our students to English texts and facilitate their engagement with English texts because language in the form of texts occurs for communication (Rustipa et al., 2021). This approach is referred to as text-based teaching. However, in practice, the implementation of text-based teaching in Indonesia has raised several issues (Triastuti, 2011).

Since the 1960s, language instruction has altered in response to the need to reform instruction so that communication is the overarching objective of instruction. The structural method was useless for teaching languages with communication in mind. In response to the flaws in the conventional structural approach to instruction, changes have been made to the curriculum and teaching methods (Mickan, 2006).

Since the adoption of a competency-based curriculum in 2004 the use of text-based instruction has increased. This is the prevailing pattern in EFL instruction and study (Arimbawa, 2012). We need to integrate linguistics into language teaching as EFL teachers. Systemic functional linguistics is the contemporary branch of linguistics. Systemic functional linguistics is where text-based instruction originates. Because communication occurs at the discourse level or text level, it places a strong emphasis on teaching and learning at that level. The ultimate aim of language education and learning is discourse or text competence (Rustipa et al., 2021).

Based on the most recent De Jager (2012), communicative competence is essential for language learners. The author contends that to effectively use language in any given context, language users must develop their linguistic skills and acquire communicative competence, also known as linguistic and

pragmatic competence. Grammatical proficiency as well as contextual or sociolinguistic proficiency are components of communication skills (Canale & Swain, 1980). Being able to understand and use a language effectively for communication purposes requires both language knowledge and proficiency (Mart, 2018). It alludes to the capacity for using words properly and making accurate statements (Mart, 2018). Therefore, being able to decide when, how, and what to say to whom is referred to as having communicative competence. The model of communicative competence put forth by Celce-Murcia (2018) includes six categories of competence: discourse, linguistic, formulaic, interactional, sociocultural, and strategic. EFL students will improve their communication skills by becoming adept at various types of texts because communicating requires utilizing a variety of spoken and written texts in the context in which they are used (Arimbawa, 2012).

This paper is a reflection on the teachers' constraints and challenges in implementing text-based teaching. The following issues were addressed in this paper: (1) What are the teacher's constraints in implementing text-based instruction? (2) What are the challenges that teachers face when implementing text-based instruction? As a result, the current study seeks to learn about teachers' constraints and challenges in implementing text-based teaching. This paper is important for broadening our perspective on text-based instruction and contributing to better implementation.

The present research examined teachers' perceptions of their experience implementing text-based teaching and revealed their constraints and challenges in achieving communicative competence, particularly in Islamic boarding schools. It is critical to reveal a teacher's perception because it will most likely influence their teaching practice. The study's findings will be shared with policymakers, who will hopefully act on them.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The limitations and difficulties in implementing text-based instruction are discussed here along with some pertinent theories and empirical evidence.

Text-based teaching implementation studies have been conducted by researchers. Here are some examples of previous research. Begin with Iftanti's (2017) research conducted at the State Islamic Institute of Tulungagung's Post Graduate Program, which claims that despite having learned English at a young age, English learners in Indonesia lack communication competence. That statement is consistent with Huda's (2016) claim that many EFL learners in Indonesia face difficulties because the language environment is hostile to them and there is no centralized national system of English education in Indonesia. The students struggled in real-world contexts with vocabulary limitations, grammar rules, and tenses confusion, as well as low motivation, according to preliminary research for the study. The teacher, on the other hand, is faced with a challenge when it comes to designing joyful classroom instruction (Iftanti, 2017). The study discovered that, as expected, text-based learning stimulated a joyful learning environment, activated student participation, and improved students' language skills. This teaching model, according to the researcher, will

not be applicable unless the teacher is committed to resolving implementation issues (Iftanti, 2017).

In an experimental study conducted at a Chinese university, the efficiency of a text-based approach and a dictionary-based approach to vocabulary instruction were compared. The study found that the text-based approach outperformed the dictionary-based approach in terms of improving learners' mastery of new words and retaining time duration in the learners' memory. The text-based approach to teaching vocabulary will be effective if the teacher can select the appropriate text and insert the new vocabulary into the text (Qian, 2011).

A mixed-method study of the text-based approach in South Africa found that while it was appropriate and beneficial for English education, it did not develop learners' communication skills. The issue arose from the English teachers' implementation of the text-based strategy without thorough understanding and awareness (Mohlabi-Tlaka, 2016). A qualitative multiple-case study showed that choosing and organizing texts for instruction can be challenging when using text-based teaching strategies. The recommendation was for teachers to receive training in both the theoretical and practical aspects of text-based instruction (Triastuti & Riazi, 2020).

The preceding studies demonstrate the efficacy of text-based instruction. However, implementation requires teachers who are knowledgeable about it and aware of its importance. The previous studies investigated the implementation of a text-based approach and the impact of text-based teaching on the educational environment on the learning outcome.

The next study on the constraints and challenges of implementing text-based teaching comes from Rustipa et al. (2021) and is titled "Text-based language teaching in the new normal era to achieve communicative competence: challenges for EFL Teachers." This is a qualitative study with 15 research participants who answered open-ended survey questions. This study included eight university teachers, four senior high school teachers, and three junior high school teachers.

According to their perspectives in Rustipa et al.'s (2021) study, all of the teachers had implemented text-based instruction. They are optimistic that proper implementation will help students improve their communication skills (Rustipa et al., 2021). However, improper implementation may prevent students from achieving communicative competence (Rustipa et al., 2021). As a result, they are both optimistic and pessimistic.

There are several challenges to implementing text-based learning, including those selecting texts, adapting and modifying texts, designing tasks, and overcoming student boredom. Students' constraints include a lack of vocabulary and grammar competence, a lack of English skills in the real context, low motivation, low interaction, and a lack of autonomy (Iftanti, 2017; Rustipa et al., 2021). On the other hand, teachers' constraints in online teaching include ICT literacy, technical issues, and internet connection (Rustipa et al., 2021). The next chapter will go into more detail.

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is a qualitative research method with a case study approach. This research aims to gain an in-depth understanding of the barriers and challenges faced by teachers and students in implementing a text-based teaching approach in specific contexts. The qualitative research method was chosen because it allows researchers to explore and understand the experiences, perceptions, and views of the research participants in depth.

The participants of this study were teachers and students involved in text-based teaching in specific contexts. The data collection techniques used in this study include in-depth interviews with teachers and students, classroom observations, and document analysis such as lesson plans and teaching materials used in text-based teaching.

The collected data were analyzed thematically. The steps of analysis included coding the data, organizing emerging themes or categories, and compiling thematic findings. This data analysis provided an in-depth understanding of the barriers and challenges faced by teachers and students in implementing a text-based teaching approach in specific contexts. In addition, this study also triangulated the data to strengthen the validity of the findings. This is done by comparing and matching findings from various data sources that have been collected.

This qualitative research method is expected to provide deeper insights into the obstacles and challenges in implementing text-based teaching in specific contexts. With a better understanding of these obstacles, it is hoped that appropriate solutions and recommendations can be found to improve the implementation of text-based teaching approaches in these specific contexts.

The preceding findings will be discussed in the following sections by interpreting and relating them to the empirical contexts, text-based approach (TBA) theory, and previous studies.

1. Constraints in Implementing Text-Based Teaching

a. Constraints by students

According to Iftanti (2017), although EFL adult students have acquired English since their primary school education level, as is prevalent among Indonesian EFL students, they continue to face numerous difficulties in English, including vocabulary, as demonstrated by studies conducted by Fauzan & Yusuf (2016) and Zuraini & Yusuf (2016), and grammar, as demonstrated by Miftah (2016), who reveals EFL students' grammatical issues in their writing practice. Furthermore, preliminary research found that postgraduate EFL students from non-English departments struggled with perceiving English tenses and applying those tenses in authentic settings. This fact lends support to Salikin's (2015) study, which reveals EFL adult learners' perceptions of failure in tenses mastery. This factual condition is consistent with the findings of Megawati et al. (2016)'s study, which shows EFL difficulties with English language skills. Many EFL students did not develop their knowledge of tenses and aspects as they learned English (Iftanti, 2017). Meanwhile, they expect to be

able to speak, write, and read fluently in English, with little difficulty with vocabulary and grammar (Iftanti, 2017). This fact primarily motivates EFL adult learners to remain silent during classroom instruction, resulting in a lack of motivation to learn English (Iftanti, 2017).

According to Rustipa et al.'s (2021) research, ten of the fifteen respondents are concerned about students' low motivation, as evidenced by their unwillingness to contribute in class. During an instructional or learning activity, for instance, some students were quiet and did not react to the commands. They also did not activate their camera during the online class.

Text-based instruction, particularly in the 'joint construction of the text' stage, necessitates student collaboration or interaction to produce a text. Eight of the fifteen participants, however, stated that collaboration in online text-based teaching was difficult (Rustipa et al., 2021). Furthermore, in the new normal era, the interaction between teachers and students was limited during online classes (Rustipa et al., 2021).

Students not only have limited interaction and collaboration, but they also have limited learning autonomy. According to the research of Rustipa et al. (2021), the 'independent construction of a text' stage, particularly in online learning, necessitates greater student autonomy. Six of the fifteen respondents stated that many students ended up failing to be self-regulated learners, and the 15th stated that she or he necessary to alert her or their students to send their tasks regularly (Rustipa et al., 2021).

This argument occurs in offline classes as well, as stated by Iftanti (2017); however, this TBL model of teaching will not be appropriate for students in elementary school as it is highly doubtful that it will be challenging to enable them to gain knowledge autonomously and work collaboratively.

b. Constraints by teacher

Fatimah and Santiana (2017) discovered that technology improved students' attitudes toward learning and teachers' professional development. A lack of ICT competencies, a slow internet connection, and technical issues are obstacles for teachers when it comes to e-learning (Rustipa et al., 2021).

According to the data collected by Rustipa et al. (2021), seven of the fifteen respondents felt they lacked ICT literacy. They stated that a lack of ICT literacy reduced their self-confidence and caused them to feel anxious (Rustipa et al., 2021). Six (40%) respondents, on the other hand, encountered technical (audio-visual quality) and internet connection issues, which caused the audio-visual to be unclear (Rustipa et al., 2021). Poor internet connection was also frequently cited as a reason for leaving class or even canceling the class (Rustipa et al., 2021).

2. Common Challenges Faced by Teachers in Implementing Text-Based Teaching

Previous research found that common challenges faced by teachers included text selection, adaptation or modification of texts, task design, and dealing with student boredom (Triastuti & Riazi, 2020; Rustipa et al., 2021). This finding is consistent with other studies that have found a lack of in-depth

conceptual and practical knowledge among English teachers to be a barrier to implementing a text-based approach (Mohlabi-Tlaka, 2016; Triastuti & Riazi, 2020). The following are the most common challenges that teachers face.

a. In selecting texts

The essential feature of text-based teaching, which emphasizes the use of authentic texts, necessitates teachers measure the degree of authenticity presented in their given texts (Triastuti & Riazi, 2020). This presents a challenge for teachers in terms of having the necessary skills and knowledge to assess the degree of text authenticity (Triastuti & Riazi, 2020). Mishan (2005) asserts that for a text to be authentic, it must reflect a specific communication purpose in its social context. The authenticity of a text is determined by its meaning in context (Triastuti & Riazi, 2020). As a consequence, it is argued that authentic texts used in language learning are difficult to achieve (Morrow, 1977 cited in Mishan, 2005; Widdowson, 1998). As revealed by the long-running debate on text authenticity in materials development (Tomlinson, 2012), providing authentic texts to learners may cause problems for EFL teachers. One argument in their favor is that authentic texts are more difficult to obtain than simplified texts (Day, 2003, cited in Triastuti & Riazi, 2020).

According to the findings of Rustipa et al. (2021), this means that the teacher should be creative to find relevant texts to use and have a stock of texts. The teacher should consider the learners' interests as well as the level of difficulty when selecting texts. Nonetheless, 11 (73%) of respondents said it was difficult to choose texts (Rustipa et al., 2021). Based on Rustipa et al. (2021), admitted to being perplexed at times about which texts drew the students' attention and whether the texts chosen were appropriate for their level. They were also perplexed as to what authentic texts entailed.

The teacher should expose the students to various types of texts in TBA; however, 5 (33%) of the respondents reported difficulty in locating different text stocks (Rustipa et al., 2021). Teachers can use text sources such as procedures for completing a task, explaining how and why things happen, reviews, arguments, debates, magazine articles, biographies, autobiographies, stories, fables, dialogs, formal/informal letters, postcards, e-mails, notices, and so on (Richards, 2005).

b. In adapting, and modifying the texts

The explanation in the previous section indicates that the learners should meet with various texts for various purposes. They will also meet with texts with various levels of authenticity, simplified, semi-authentic, and authentic texts. And the teacher should have text-adaptation strategies. Based on the data from Rustipa et al. (2021), adapting or modifying texts is also problematic for EFL teachers. Fourteen of the fifteen respondents said that they had problems adapting texts (Rustipa et al., 2021). This is because language teaching cannot replicate absolute authenticity in texts (Morrow, 1977, cited in Mishan, 2005) or the reality embedded in texts (Widdowson, 1998). Burns (2012) supports this claim by claiming that analyzing text authenticity is a difficult task for teachers.

When presenting texts, teachers may become trapped by using "trivial examples of daily survival communication in contrast to more complex, hybrid, or ideologically charged texts..." (Burns, 2012, p. 146), or by text simplification that leads to "a distortion of natural language" (McDonough & Shaw, 2003, p. 82).

Text adaptation is a time-consuming and complicated process. Teachers are sometimes unsure whether the adapted text accurately reflects the original text (Rustipa et al., 2021). Adaptation strategies reduce the level of difficulty or complexity of the texts and match them to our learning objectives (Rustipa et al., 2021). Some of the strategies include shortening, segmenting, simplifying, co-textualizing, and glossing (Thornbury, 2005).

c. In designing the tasks

When designing tasks that can impede communicative competence achievement, teachers face challenges. According to the findings of Rustipa et al. (2021), thirteen of the fifteen respondents reported difficulty with task design, and three teachers stated that they occasionally ran out of ideas for tasks to assign at each stage of TBA. Teachers want their students to participate in interesting and challenging activities at all stages of TBA (Rustipa et al., 2021). They do, however, occasionally run out of task ideas that will challenge students and motivate them to work hard in class (Rustipa et al., 2021).

As part of the context-building stage, the teacher can raise students' awareness of the wordings, grammar, and text types they will encounter later in the lesson (Rustipa et al., 2021). The purpose of presenting model texts during the modeling stage is to get students to observe, experience, and process the texts (Rustipa et al., 2021). The teacher can help students become familiar with texts by having them read or listen to several examples of the same type (Rustipa et al., 2021).

Texts selected for text-based instruction are meant to encourage students to actively participate in the classroom by responding to the texts. The teacher and students collaborate to analyze texts to help students develop their discourse or language resources (Rustipa et al., 2021). They can look at the lexicogrammar, schematic structure, communicative purpose, and other aspects of the text (Rustipa et al., 2021). Following this text analysis, the teacher can proceed with explicit teaching in which they introduce and explain technical terms, grammar, and so on.

d. Students' boredom with routine

According to the findings of the research conducted by Rustipa et al. (2021), three of the fifteen respondents stated that using the five-phase cycle to teach all English language skills sometimes bored the students. The students had a good idea of what the teachers expected of them (Rustipa et al., 2021). This is supported by Marina and Marmiené 's (2019) discovery that having to repeatedly use a five-phase cycle for second language learners may be tiresome. Nonetheless, they serve as a reminder that the benefits of the five-phase cycle outweigh the drawbacks (Marina & Marmiené, 2006). Teachers must be creative and innovative to avoid boredom, such as changing the cycles and incorporating various multimedia to engage students (Rustipa et al., 2021).

This, however, does not apply to adult learners. According to Iftanti (2017), the TBL instructional model as a whole creates a joyful learning environment, which increases motivation among EFL adult learners to learn English, but this is difficult for elementary school students because they prefer something that is not monotonous and requires learning autonomy and cooperation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the data and literature presented above, we can conclude that text-based teaching has a significant impact on EFL teaching and learning principles, as well as improving students' meaning-making abilities because the text-based approach assists students in developing communication competence in an authentic environment. Based on these benefits, EFL teachers are encouraged to use text-based instruction. Nonetheless, teachers and students face constraints and challenges when putting this approach into practice. Some of the constraints are a lack of vocabulary and grammar mastery, a lack of English skills in context, a lack of motivation, a lack of learning autonomy, and a lack of collaboration. The challenges for the teacher, on the other hand, are selecting the authentic text, modifying and adapting the authentic text, designing the task, and students' boredom with routine. To overcome these obstacles, teachers should engage in in-depth learning about how and what to do to put a text-based approach into practice. As a result, policymakers are advised to provide advanced training in this context so that teachers can provide their best teaching practice.

The author suggests that a more extensive study be conducted on this subject. Some of the previous research studies only covered a limited number of participants, so further research should be conducted.

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